

PREDICTION OF FAILURE MODES OF FIBROUS COMPOSITE MATERIALS

G.A. Abu-Farsakh and Y.A. Abdel-Jawad
Civil Engineering Department
Jordan University of Science & Technology

ABSTRACT

An energy based failure criterion has been, recently, developed by the authors. At any stress level, the model deals with the actual composite material as an equivalent linear elastic material. The total strain energy density of the system is considered to be composed of two parts; elastic, and plastic. In this paper, the model has been used to identify the modes of failure based on the relative magnitudes of the various energy terms appearing in the failure criterion equation. Accordingly, three types of failure are anticipated; fiber failure, matrix failure (tension or compression), and matrix failure in shear. The critical fiber orientation for a given stress state can be predicted as well.

As an example, boron-epoxy Narmco 5505 is considered in the present study. The failure envelopes are predicted using several stress combinations for fiber-orientation ranging from 0° to 90° . Four failure modes are detected; classified as: mode A,B,C and D .

Keywords: failure criterion, composite materials, failure modes, strain energy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composites are characterized for their high stiffness-to-weight ratio which depend on fiber orientation angle. Developing theoretical models to predict failure strengths of such materials has provided a necessary tool for a better understanding of material behavior and design.

A significant number of failure criteria has been proposed in the literature [1-6]. Recently, an extensive survey of the different failure criteria has been conducted by Labossiere and Neale [7].

Several approaches have been used to model the behavior of cracked laminates and to study the effect of interlaminar cracks on laminates' loading carrying capacity. Some researchers [8-10] have suggested to modify the material behavior in the failure direction, assuming a softening response in that direction.

A constitutive model [11] was developed based on a continuum mechanics approach, which predicts the nonlinear behavior of laminated composites up to and including the ultimate failure. Using this model, three modes of failure can be identified

based on the relative magnitudes of the various stress-ratio terms appearing in the failure criterion. These modes of failure are: fiber failure, matrix failure (tension or compression), and matrix shear failure.

Christensen [12] has introduced a tensor form failure criterion applicable to thick laminates of restricted transversely isotropic composites. Hence, reducing the independent material property constants from five to three. The model formulation is composed of a minimum number of failure parameters and provides an idea about the failure modes.

In a previous work [13], the authors have developed an energy based failure criterion using an equivalent linear elastic material. The proposed model is capable of predicting stresses and strains at failure with no restriction on the material properties. The failure envelope at each stress level can, also, be obtained.

The main objective of this paper is to determine the modes of failure as affected by the angle of fiber orientation.

2. FAILURE MODEL

A new failure criterion has been proposed in a previous work by the authors [13]. The two-dimensional form of the model is given as:

$$\left(\frac{U_1}{U_{1m}}\right)_k + \left(\frac{U_2}{U_{2m}}\right)_k + \left(\frac{U_{12}}{U_{12m}}\right) = 1.0 \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where, k is either tension or compression.

The U_1 and U_2 terms appeared in Eq. 1 are defined as the extensional strain energy densities in 1 and 2 principal material directions, respectively. The term U_{12} is defined as the shear strain energy density in 1-2 plane. The subscript m indicates the corresponding maximum value obtained from test data in the principal material directions. All the U_i parameters are obtained based on an assumed equivalent linear elastic material. For more details on the subject consult Ref. [5].

The stress-type, compression or tension, is specified according to the stress sign convention;

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &> 0.0, \text{ tension in 1 - direction} \\ \sigma_2 &> 0.0, \text{ tension in 2 - direction} \\ \sigma_1 &< 0.0, \text{ compression in 1 - direction} \dots\dots\dots \\ \sigma_2 &< 0.0, \text{ compression in 2 - direction} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

If a lamina is made of a generally orthotropic material, and is subject to stresses σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} , the stresses σ_1 , σ_2 and τ_{12} in the principal material directions are obtained using the following transformation relations:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= \sigma_x \cos^2 \theta + \sigma_y \sin^2 \theta + \tau_{xy} \sin 2\theta \\ \sigma_2 &= \sigma_x \sin^2 \theta + \sigma_y \cos^2 \theta - \tau_{xy} \sin 2\theta \\ \tau_{12} &= 1/2 [(-\sigma_x + \sigma_y) \sin 2\theta] + \tau_{xy} [\cos^2 \theta - \sin^2 \theta] \end{aligned} \quad \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

3. FAILURE MODES

Re-writing Eq.1 in a simplified form it will appear as:

$$\bar{U}_{1k} + \bar{U}_{2k} + \bar{U}_{12} = 1.0 \quad \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

where, k specifies the type of stress (compressive or tensile) according to relations (2). From now on, the subscript k will be omitted for the sake of notation simplicity. The ratios \bar{U}_i are expressed as:

$$\bar{U}_i = U_i / U_{im}, \quad i = 1, 2, 12 \quad \dots\dots\dots (5)$$

Three types of failure are classified according to the dominant energy - ratio. The first failure type is in the fiber direction and is determined by \bar{U}_1 . The second type which is determined by \bar{U}_2 is a matrix failure in the transverse direction. The last type is a matrix shear failure determined by the ratio \bar{U}_{12} .

For better understanding of lamina failure modes, the values of energy ratios \bar{U}_1 , \bar{U}_2 , and \bar{U}_{12} are plotted versus the angle of fiber orientation (θ°). Accordingly, three graphs are obtained for each lamina under a given combination of σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} . At failure, the normal stresses σ_x and σ_y are located on a closed envelope obtained at a specific shear stress value τ_{xy} . The stress σ_y is obtained as a ratio R_y of σ_x such that:

$$\sigma_y = \pm R_y \cdot \sigma_x \quad \dots\dots\dots (6)$$

At the intersection of any two curves, a critical angle (θ_c) is obtained. Generally two points of intersection are obtained, (modes A,B,C as shown in Figs. 1-3). However, in some cases, there are no intersections, in such case a single energy ratio is the dominant one, for example Mode D in Fig. 4. Therefore, the highest energy ratio at each orientation angle is considered as a representative of the expected failure mode related to that energy ratio. For example, if the \bar{U}_1 - ratio is the highest ratio at a certain θ° , then a fiber failure type is expected to take place.

Different combinations of energy-curve intersections may be obtained for each material, depending on type and magnitude of loading. Table 1 classifies four failure modes (mode A,B,C and D) which occur in the case of boron-epoxy fiber composite material. These modes are, also, illustrated in Figs. 1 through 4.

Table 1. Failure modes and their corresponding energy envelopes

Failure Mode	Energy Envelope
A	$\bar{U}_1, \bar{U}_{12}, \bar{U}_2$
B	$\bar{U}_{12}, \bar{U}_1, \bar{U}_{12}$
C	$\bar{U}_{12}, \bar{U}_2, \bar{U}_{12}$
D	\bar{U}_2

4. NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND DISCUSSION

As an example of composite materials, the failure of boron-epoxy lamina is studied. The material mechanical properties are given in Table 1. Three cases are considered with different combinations of σ_x , σ_y and τ_{xy} .

Table 2. Mechanical properties of boron-epoxy

Material Properties			
σ_1	max.	1.342	GPa
σ_2	max.	0.0538	GPa
τ_{12}	max.	0.0642	GPa
E_1		207	GPa
E_2		19.8	MPa
G_{12}		5.52	MPa

Case (1)

The stress-ratio R_y is taken equal to zero with shear stresses varying from -41.4 MPa to $+41.4$ MPa, as shown in Table 3. In this case, two critical angles θ_1 and θ_2 are detected. The failure mode is classified as mode A where, \bar{U}_1 - failure is dominant from $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq \theta_1$, \bar{U}_{12} - failure is dominant from $\theta_1 \leq \theta \leq \theta_2$ and \bar{U}_2 - failure is dominant for $\theta_2 \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$. A representative example for this case is shown in Fig. 1 for $R_y = 0.0$, and $\tau_{xy} = 20.7$ MPa.

Fig.1. Normalized failure energy ratios versus angle of fiber orientation (θ°) for boron-epoxy ;

Narmco 5505 ; $\tau_{xy} = 20.7$ MPa, $R_y = 0$, Mode A.

Case (2)

The stress-ratio R_y is taken greater than zero with shear stresses varying from -41.4 MPa to +41.4 MPa. As indicated in Table 3, the dominant energy mode, in this case, is the σ_2 failure mode; classified as mode D. No intersection is observed between the energy curves (see Fig. 4).

Table 3. Critical orientation angles and failure modes for boron-epoxy (shear from -41.4 MPa to +41.4 MPa).

Shear (MPa)	$R_y = 0.0$			$R_y > 0.0$
	θ_1	θ_2	Mode	Mode
-41.4	2	23	A	D
-20.7	3	28	A	D
0.0	4	36	A	D
+20.7	5	49	A	D
+41.4	6	71	A	D

Case (3)

In this case, the shear stress value is assigned a high value of 62.1 MPa close to the ultimate shear strength of boron-epoxy ($\tau_u = 64.2$ MPa). The effect of changing the sign of shear stress is also considered. The stress-ratio R_y is varied between 0.0 and 5. The dominant energy-ratio in this case is the one corresponding to mode C, except the failure mode at $R_y = 0.0$ and $\tau_{xy} = +62.1$ MPa; where mode B is the dominant one, as shown in Table 4. The difference between modes B and C is that at $\theta_1 < \theta < \theta_2$, the σ_1 -failure in mode B is replaced by σ_2 -failure in mode C, while the σ_2 -failure remains dominant at all other angles.

Table 4. Critical orientation angles and failure modes for boron-epoxy (shear -62.1 MPa and +62.1 MPa, $R_y \leq 5$).

R_y	Shear = -62.1 MPa			Shear = +62.1 MPa		
	θ_1	θ_2	Mode	θ_1	θ_2	Mode
0.0	19	30	C	3	8	B
0.2	17.5	29	C	3	33	C
0.4	16	28.5	C	5	54	C
0.6	15	27.5	C	8	66	C
0.8	14	27	C	11	73	C
1.0	13.5	26.5	C	14	76	C
2.0	12	24	C	29	83.5	C
3.0	11.5	23.5	C	41.5	86	C
4.0	11	23	C	51	86.5	C
5.0	10.5	22.5	C	57.5	87	C

Fig.2. Normalized failure energy ratios versus angle of fiber orientation (θ°) for boron-epoxy

Narmco 5505 ; $\tau_{xy} = 62.1$ MPa, $R_y = 0$, Mode B.

Fig.3. Normalized failure energy ratios versus angle of fiber orientation (θ°) for boron-epoxy

Narmco 5505 ; $\tau_{xy} = 62.1$ MPa, $R_y = 1$, Mode C.

Fig. 4. Normalized failure energy ratios versus angle of orientation (θ°) for boron-epoxy Narmco 5505 ; $\tau_{xy} = 41.4$ MPa, $R_y = 1$, Mode D.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Failure modes of boron-epoxy fiber reinforced composite were predicted based on the relative magnitudes of various energy terms appearing in the failure criterion equation. Using this approach three types of failure are anticipated; fiber failure, matrix failure (tension or compression, and matrix failure in shear. Any one of these types may take place, depending on the stress state and the fiber orientation angle.

6. REFERENCES

1. Tsai, S.W., *Strength Theories of Filamentary Structures*, Fundamental Aspects of Fiber Reinforced Plastic Composites, Edited by R.T. Schwartz, and H.S. Schwartz, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1968, pp. 3-11.
2. Jones, R.M., *Mechanics of Composite Materials*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1979.
3. Tsai, S.W. and Han, H.T., *Introduction to Composite Materials*, Technomic Publishing Company, Westport, 1980.
4. Jiang, Z., and Tennyson, R.C. *Closure of Cubic Tensor Polynomial Failure Surface*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 23, pp. 208-231, 1989.

5. Abu-Farsakh, G.A., *New Material Models for Nonlinear Stress-Strain Behavior of Composite Materials*, Composites. Vol. 20, No.4, pp. 349-360, 1989.
6. Feng, W.W., *A Failure Criterion for Composite Materials*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 25, pp.83-100, 1991.
7. Labossiere, P. and Neale, K.W., *Macroscopic Failure Criteria for Fiber-Reinforced Composite Materials*, Solid Mechanics Archives, Vol. 12, No.2, pp. 65-95, 1987.
8. Petit, P.H. and Waddoups, M.E., *A Method of Predicting the Nonlinear Behavior of Laminated Composites*. Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 3, pp. 2-19, 1969.
9. Chiu, K.D., *Ultimate Strengths of Laminated Composites*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.3, pp. 578-582, 1969.
10. Lee, J.D., *Three Dimensional Finite Element Analysis of Damage Accumulation in Composite Laminates*, Computers and Structures, Vol. 15, 1982, pp. 335-350.
11. Vaziri, R., Olson, M.D., and Anderson, D.L., *A Plasticity Based Constitutive Model for Fiber-Reinforced Composite Laminates*, Journal of Composite Materials, vol. 22, pp. 874-897, 1988.
12. Christensen, R.M., *Tesnor Transformations and Failure Criteria for the Analysis of Fiber Composite Materials*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 22, pp. 874-897, 1988.
13. Abu-Farsakh, G.A., and Abdel-Jawad, Y.A., *A New Failure Criterion for Nonlinear Composite Materials*, Submitted for Journal Publication, 1992.